

Research article

Phosphorus speciation in different sewage sludges and their biochars and its implications for movement of labile phosphate in two soils

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Biochar

Sewage sludge

Phosphorus speciation

XANES

³¹P NMR

Phosphorus mobility

ABSTRACT

It is essential to understand the P dynamics of recycled biomaterials, like biochar derived from sewage sludge, especially with potential application as fertilizers. The objective of this study was to understand how pyrolysis affects the speciation of P in sewage sludge and thereby the effect on labile P pools and mobility of P in soil. The P speciation and lability of two sewage sludges (one biologically treated and one iron-precipitated) and their biochars (pyrolyzed at 400 °C and 600 °C) were determined by liquid state ³¹P nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, X-ray absorption near edge spectroscopy, and sequential chemical extraction. These biomaterials were applied in a concentrated band to two soils, and P lability was studied in the adjacent soil at varying distances.

Speciation techniques showed P was more closely associated with Ca and Fe for the iron-precipitated sludge and its biochars than the biologically treated sludge and its biochars. Instead, the P in the biologically treated biochars was found to be largely (40% or more) in polymeric forms (pyro- or poly-phosphates). The relationship between the speciation and the mobility of P in soil (as assessed by incubating biomaterials in a one-dimensional reaction system) was more evident when incubating the sewage sludges than the respective biochars. Particularly, the biologically treated sludge had a high proportion of labile P (56% water-extractable P), as determined by sequential extraction, and upon incubation, it was also the only material where water-extractable P remained significantly above the control soil level up to 3 mm from the biomaterial layer. After pyrolysis, this lability decreased significantly (up to a 25-fold decrease in water-extractable P), and this was reflected in the immobility of P in the biochars during incubation in the two soils. Differences in speciation between biochars were not reflected in the incubation experiment, as the differences in P release and mobility were not significant.

1. Introduction

Rock phosphate, used for phosphorus (P) fertilizers, is a limited resource and is currently used unsustainably (Cordell and White, 2014; Egle et al., 2016; Jupp et al., 2021; Reitzel et al., 2019). The EU's listing of phosphate rock as a critical raw material reflects this challenge (EC, 2014). Preventing the depletion of rock phosphate resources requires the prevention of losses and increased recycling of P. A growing source of P recycling is urban sewage sludge, in concentrated radii of increasingly urbanized areas (van Dijk et al., 2016). Controversial debates and policy changes in, for example, Switzerland, where direct application of

sewage sludge to agricultural fields is now prohibited due to the potential risk of organic contaminants, suggest that the general acceptance of using sewage sludge as a fertilizer may be changing (Kelessidis and Stasinakis, 2012; Magid et al., 2020). This has stimulated interest in sanitation methods, including the thermochemical treatment of sewage sludge by pyrolysis, which involves heating material under an inert atmosphere to produce bio-gas, bio-oil and solid biochar (Agrafioti et al., 2013). Biochar offers potential benefits in terms of removing organic pollutants and stabilizing heavy metals, increasing total P concentrations, generating stable carbon, and ease of storage and transport (Agrafioti et al., 2013; Buss, 2021; Leiva-Suárez et al., 2021;

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.122565>

Received 27 May 2024; Received in revised form 29 August 2024; Accepted 16 September 2024

Available online 26 September 2024

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Praspaliauskas et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2022a).

Recycling of P from sewage sludge through biochar production requires insight into the mechanisms by which the phosphate can become plant available in soil. Only P that ultimately becomes soluble ionic orthophosphates (H_2PO_4^- , HPO_4^{2-} , and PO_4^{3-}) can cross the cell membrane of plant roots and is considered available for plants (Kruse et al., 2015). However, P added in other forms will possibly become available in the soil depending on the chemical P speciation in the fertilizer and its interactions with the soil (Kratz et al., 2019; Weihrach and Opp, 2018). Therefore, recycling of P through the application of sewage sludge biochar to soil requires investigation of the P composition in the biomaterials and their plant-availability.

The P speciation in soils and biomaterials is determined by many factors. P sorption sites in soil can vary with the elements available in the natural bedrock, as influenced by soil texture, pH, redox potential, and cation/anion exchange capacity (Amberger, 1996; Prasad et al., 2017). The persistence of different organic P species within a soil system depends on the extent to which these species are mineralized, which is often also influenced by the aforementioned factors of pH, redox potential, etc. (Belinque et al., 2015; Dinh et al., 2016; Nash et al., 2014). Inorganic P speciation is determined by equilibria between precipitates, adsorbed forms of P and phosphates in the pore water. Iron (Fe), aluminum (Al), calcium (Ca), and magnesium (Mg) are particularly important for phosphate mineral formation and sorption (Barrow, 2021; Fink et al., 2016; Samadi, 2006; Weihrach and Opp, 2018). The chemical composition and P speciation of sewage sludge biochars is strongly influenced by the original sewage sludge feedstock. Particularly the phosphate removal method used in the wastewater treatment plant (Fe, Al, biological P removal, or combinations of the three) influences the mineral phases and the subsequent P availability of both sewage sludge and derived products (Delin, 2016; Falk Øgaard and Brod, 2016; Krogstad et al., 2005; Lemming et al., 2020). The availability of P in sewage sludge biochars has mainly been studied using methods such as sequential extractions and pot growth studies (Gondek et al., 2019; Mackay et al., 2017; Paneque et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2012; Ylivainio et al., 2021).

More detailed chemical characterization methods to study P availability in sewage sludge biochars can provide deeper mechanistic insights. These include methods that determine the organic species such as liquid state NMR and speciation methods for inorganic forms such as XRD, XANES, IR and Raman spectroscopy, and elemental correlation analyses (Huang and Tang, 2015; Mahdi et al., 2019; Robinson et al., 2018). Using XRD, NMR and sequential extraction, Qian & Jiang et al. (2014) found that both organic and inorganic P species can be present in sewage sludges, although after dewatering at wastewater treatment plants, most of the P in sludge is often orthophosphate. Organophosphates are degraded and fully converted to inorganic phosphates, including pyrophosphates, above 400 °C (Qian and Jiang, 2014; Zhu et al., 2022). While some suggest that the polymeric phosphates degrade and are converted to orthophosphates at higher temperatures, Qian et al. (2022) found increased formation of polyphosphates at 700 °C pyrolysis compared to 400 °C. This suggests a dynamic equilibrium that depends on the feedstock and pyrolysis conditions, and an apparent complexity that makes it relevant to consider P speciation in any newly produced biochar.

In addition, links between such P speciation in biomaterials and phosphate dissolution and mobility, upon addition to different soils have yet to be established. There has been recognition of the importance of understanding the release of phosphorus from fertilizers, particularly to support efficient fertilizer management (Degryse and McLaughlin, 2014; McBeath et al., 2012; Meyer et al., 2023). Hitherto, studies have shown that the diffusion of phosphorus from fertilizers into soils depends on the labile P in the fertilizers, the water content of the soil, the sorption capacity of the soil, and the phosphorus concentration gradient between fertilizer and soil (Degryse and McLaughlin, 2014; Eghball et al., 1990; McBeath et al., 2012; Meyer et al., 2023; Olsen and Watanabe, 1963).

Factors such as clay content, pH, etc., in the soil that determine the sorption of phosphorus and therefore P speciation in soils, then determine how far P can diffuse from the application site (Meyer et al., 2021). On longer timescales the solubility of the added P species in the soil is likely to affect mobility and plant uptake.

Overall, new insights into the agronomic and environmental consequences of applying these biomaterials to different soils contribute to creating a viable circular phosphorus economy with recycled fertilizer products. The overall objectives of this study were (1) to understand how pyrolysis affects the speciation of P in sewage sludges differing in P removal method and (2) how this subsequently affects the bioavailability and mobility of P in soils over different time periods.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Soil samples

Two P-depleted soils were collected from sites in Denmark. Relevant soil characteristics of both soils are provided in Table 1. The first soil was collected from the unfertilized treatment of a long-term field trial at the University of Copenhagen's experimental farm in Taastrup. This soil is classified as a sandy loam soil and it has not been fertilized for over 20 years (Lemming et al., 2019). The second soil, a loamy sand, was collected in Jerslev in North Jutland. In Denmark, the optimal P status of agricultural soils is defined as having 20–40 mg kg⁻¹ Olsen P (extracted by 0.5 M bicarbonate, pH 8.5) (Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark, 2017). Table 1 shows that the sandy soil falls within this range, although in practice, P deficiency in plants grown on this soil is observed. We chose these soils to highlight the effects of contrasting textures and p saturation. Both soils were air-dried and sieved to 2 mm after sampling. The soils are referred to throughout the paper as loamy soil and sandy soil, respectively.

2.1.2. Biomaterials

Two sewage sludges with different properties were collected. The first one was a biologically treated sewage sludge (without chemical precipitants) obtained from the Gårdeby wastewater treatment plant in Aabenraa, Denmark. While this sludge receives inputs from municipal waste streams, it is also made up of waste coming from dairy and bread industry (H. Hansen, personal communication, October 19, 2023). The other sludge was a dewatered sewage sludge from the Biofos wastewater

Table 1

pH (measured in water) and texture (measured in the top 25 cm of the soils) of the loamy and sandy soil, as well as relevant elemental concentrations (for methods see Section S1). Subscripts 'ox' indicate derived concentrations from ammonium oxalate extractions (Rose et al., 2019). P_{sat} gives the degree of P saturation (Section S1).

Soil	Unit	Loamy	Sandy
N	%	0.15 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.01
C		1.51 ± 0.10	4.26 ± 0.21
pH	-	6.0	5.8
Clay	%	12.6 ^a	6.5
Silt	%	14.3 ^a	9.0
Fine sand	%	43.6 ^a	72.2
Coarse sand	%	26.2 ^a	4.4
Total P	mg kg ⁻¹	443	665
Olsen P		15 ± 0.7	49 ± 6.2
Al _{ox}	mmol kg ⁻¹	32 ± 2	109 ± 18
Fe _{ox}	mmol kg ⁻¹	60 ± 4	49 ± 10
Mn _{ox}	mmol kg ⁻¹	8 ± 1	2 ± 1
P _{ox}	mmol kg ⁻¹	9 ± 1	22 ± 4
Si _{ox}	mmol kg ⁻¹	9 ± 1	8 ± 2
P _{sat}		0.19	0.27

^a Values obtained from Lemming et al. (2019).

treatment plant in Copenhagen, Denmark. This wastewater was treated with FeClSO_4 to precipitate phosphate after enhanced biological P removal. Prior to pyrolysis, sewage sludges were frozen down in sealed containers for storage. Biochar was produced from each sewage sludge at 400 °C and 600 °C using a laboratory batch pyrolysis oven (31 cm × 10 cm × 16 cm pyrolysis reactor). The maximum pyrolysis temperatures of 400 °C and 600 °C were chosen because 600 °C is a common temperature for commercial biochar production in Denmark, and biochar produced at lower temperatures is more likely to contain phosphorus in more available forms (Figueiredo et al., 2021; Freitas et al., 2023; Qian et al., 2022; Qian and Jiang, 2014). Three aluminum trays, each containing about 100 g of oven-dried (105 °C, not ground) sludge were placed in the reactor, sealed, and flushed with N_2 (1.5 L min^{-1}) for 10 min at ambient temperature. A heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} was employed to bring the reactor to the maximum pyrolysis temperature, where it remained for 30 min. After that, the biochar product was left in the pyrolysis oven under an inert atmosphere until temperatures reached below 100 °C. Thereafter, the products were left to cool under ambient atmosphere and stored in air-tight and opaque containers. The biologically treated sludge is subsequently referred to as BioSS and the derived biochars as Bio400 and Bio600 according to their temperature treatment. Similarly, FeSS, Fe400, and Fe600 are abbreviations for the iron precipitated sludge and derived biochars.

All materials were analyzed for elemental composition using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, Agilent 5100). To prepare samples, sludges (dried at 105 °C) and biochars were placed in plastic containers (250 ml) with three zirconia balls and ball-milled for about 7 min (Fluid management, Skandex SO-40a, Sassenheim) to a fine powder. They were then microwave digested (Ultrawave, Milestone Inc) with HNO_3 , H_2O_2 , and HF. For C and N analysis the dried and ground materials were analyzed using an elemental analyzer.

2.2. XRD and SEM-EDS

Sludges (dried at 105 °C) and biochars were placed in plastic containers (250 ml) with three zirconia balls and ball-milled for about 7 min (Fluid management, Skandex SO-40a, Sassenheim) to a fine powder. For XRD, samples were then measured using a PANalytical X'Pert Pro MPD powder diffractometer. The diffractometer used $\text{Co-K}\alpha$ radiation ($\text{K}\alpha_1 = 1.789 \text{ \AA}$, 40 kV and 40 mA) with a continuous scan mode (PW3011/10 detector, 2θ range from 5° to 90°, step size $0.02^\circ/\text{step}$ and 5 s/step). For SEM-EDS, samples were mounted on carbon tape and coated with carbon for analysis. The SEM-EDS was acquired by a Zeiss Evo SEM with an acceleration voltage of 15 kV (the technical details including the energy of the electron beam and the working distance are found on the figures in Table S2). The EDS signal was collected by a silicon drift detector provided by Oxford Instruments.

2.3. XANES P K-edge

XANES P K-edge spectra of the biomaterials were obtained at the Taiwan Light Source (TLS-16 A) in Hsinchu City, Taiwan. The beam size is $0.25 \times 0.16 \text{ mm}$. The data were processed (normalized with the same pre- and post-edge range) for linear combination fitting (LCF) using Athena 0.9.26. Sludge samples were freeze-dried prior to analysis. The standards used for LCF were measured at the beamline and are listed in Section S2, alongside any other sample preparation. Based on the result of principle component analysis (PCA), a maximum of four standards were used for LCFs, considering the limited degrees of freedom and the independence of each spectrum. P K-edge standards used for LCFs in this experiment were hydroxyapatite, amorphous calcium phosphate, vivianite, variscite phytate, Na-pyrophosphate, and struvite. During PCA analysis, hydroxyapatite, vivianite, and variscite proved to represent similar spectral features as $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. Therefore hydroxyapatite could be used interchangeably with $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, vivianite with $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and variscite with

$\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ during LCF, dependent on which standard gave the best fit. The fitting range used for the P K edge was -20 – 40 eV (relative to the P absorption edge of 2146 eV). All standards for the Fe K edge were used in LCFs and the fitting range used was -20-70 eV (relative to the Fe absorption edge of 7112 eV). The absorption edge of P was calibrated with Zr foil (L3-edge, 2222.3 eV) and that of Fe was calibrated with Fe foil (K-edge, 7112 eV). The scanning energy ranges were -36-200 eV for P and -200-797 eV for Fe.

2.4. Liquid state ^{31}P NMR spectroscopy

The extraction procedure for liquid state ^{31}P NMR followed the procedure of Staal et al. (2019) for sludge, which showed that an EDTA pre-extraction extracted only Fe-bound P in sludge, but not biogenic P or polyphosphates, while simultaneously improving the subsequent NaOH extraction and signal clarity. We note that not all organic or polymeric species may be extracted, and some organic species may be altered by the extraction (e.g. changes to DOM aggregation, hydrolysis of orthophosphate diesters or polyphosphates), see Wang and Nielsen, 2020 for a detailed discussion. Sludges and biochars were first extracted with 0.05 mol L^{-1} EDTA, followed by 0.25 mol L^{-1} NaOH, the latter of which was used for spectral analysis (Section S3). Extraction efficiencies are given in Section S3 Table S1. The ^{31}P NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL CZ 500 R 500 MHz (11.7 T) spectrometer (Japan) with a 5 mm double resonance probe (202.4 MHz Larmor frequency for ^{31}P). Spectra were obtained using a 45° excitation pulse and a relaxation delay time of 10 s. 1400 (2450) scans were obtained for the sludges (biochars) respectively. The ^{31}P NMR spectra were referenced relative to concentrated (85%) phosphoric acid ($\delta = 0 \text{ ppm}$).

2.5. Sequential extraction

A modified version of the Hedley fractionation procedure was used to assess the labile P pools within biomaterials (Alvarenga et al., 2017; Hedley et al., 1982). Briefly, 0.35 g (dry matter) of biomaterial was added to 35 mL of extractant and shaken on an end-over-end shaker (35 rpm) for 16 h and centrifuged (5 min at 9000 rpm), after which the supernatant was filtered through Whatman no. 5 filter paper (2.5 μm pore size). The solids remaining in the tubes were used for the subsequent extraction. The extractants used were MilliQ water, 0.5 mol L^{-1} NaHCO_3 , 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOH and 1 mol L^{-1} HCl. Orthophosphate concentrations in the extracts were analyzed colorimetrically (using the molybdenum blue method) on a flow injection analyzer (FIAstar 5000, Foss Analytical, Denmark).

Total phosphorus in each fraction was measured to elucidate potential organic phosphorus species, as well as pyro- and polyphosphates (Condrón and Newman, 2011). Briefly, samples (5 ml) were digested with a potassium persulphate oxidizing solution (0.5 ml) in an autoclave for 55 min (120 °C, 220 kPa) (according to Pote et al., 2009) and the P content was then measured colorimetrically as described above. If the total P fraction after oxidation was found to be smaller than the inorganic P in the sample due to measurement uncertainty, the fraction was assumed not to contain any organic species. Phosphorus in the solid residuals was not measured but was calculated based on the total P content. Measurement inaccuracies can therefore lead to negative values for the P that is not accounted for.

2.6. One dimensional slicing incubations

Fig. S1 provides a schematic of the incubation setups used to reflect the mobility of P across the biomaterial/soil interface. Set-ups were similar to those used by Sica et al. (2023). Two plastic discs (18 mm h and \varnothing 59 mm) were packed with soil at 50% water holding capacity (WHC) and to a density of $1.3 \text{ g}_{\text{DW}} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Then biomaterials were placed between the two soil discs. The height of the biomaterial layer was adjusted to 2 mm for all biomaterials. The sludges were air-dried to

approximately the same water content (75–80%). FeSS and all biochars were added in an amount to provide 40 mg total P, while 25 mg total P was added with the BioSS, as this best fitted into the 2 mm biomaterial layer. The biochars were mixed with sand (about 7 g dry weight) at 50% WHC to achieve a volume of 2 mm height with a bulk density of $1.3 \text{ g}_{\text{DW}} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. For each incubation time, control set-up was included, from which 7 data points were obtained at the same distances as the other set-ups.

The soil columns were taped together, and the ends were wrapped with a single strip of tape to ensure that the soil remained within the discs during handling. The columns were randomly placed in a container with a lid, with a wet towel on the side (not in contact with the soil) at 15°C . The discs were randomly shuffled once a week. At the end of the incubation period, the halves were separated and sliced with razor blades on a rotating piston that, with turns, successively pushed the soil out of the plastic rings to obtain 1–2 mm slices. Soils at the same distance from the biomaterials, but at opposite ends of the discs were pooled for measurements. All treatments were set up in triplicate. Incubations were performed for two, four, and 14 weeks (in separate batches) to determine how P mobility changed over time.

2.7. Chemical analysis following one dimensional incubation

Following slicing, soil and biomaterial samples were analyzed for pH and water-extractable P. The pH was measured by shaking samples on an end-over-end shaker (35 rpm) with MilliQ water (1:5 w/v ratio) for 1 h, followed by sedimentation for 1 h and measurement with a pH meter. Water extractable P was measured by extracting an amount corresponding to 0.75 g dry weight of soil with 45 mL of MilliQ water (1:60 w/v ratio) in a 50 mL centrifuge tube. This was shaken for 1 h (35 rpm) and filtered through a Whatman no. 5 filter paper. The concentrations of orthophosphate present in the solution after filtration were determined colorimetrically on a flow injection analyzer (FIAstar 5000, Foss Analytical, Denmark). Water extractable P was used as a proxy for bioavailable P (Kratz et al., 2016; Lemming et al., 2017), which represents a pool of soil P that is potentially environmentally mobile and available for plant uptake and nutrition.

2.8. Statistical analysis

Statistics were carried out in R 4.2.3 version. For each treatment, incubation period, and soil in the incubation experiment, a *t*-test (with holm *p*-adjusted values) was performed to compare the means of the water extractable P at each distance (up until 5 mm) to the control soil level, to understand whether P coming from the biomaterial was mobile.

3. Results

3.1. Basic elemental analysis of biomaterials

Table 2 provides basic information on the elemental composition of all materials used, with Fe, Al, Mg, and Ca included as P may be

Table 2

Elemental composition of biomaterials as measured using microwave digestion (Ultrawave, Milestone Inc) with HNO_3 , H_2O_2 , and HF and subsequent analysis by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, Agilent 5100). Then molar ratios of P and the major elements in mineral phases are given as well as the water content (WC) as related to fresh weight. C and N measurements are given in % dry matter.

	WC	N	C	P	Fe	Al	Mg	Ca	Al:P	Ca:P	Fe:P	Mg:P
	%			($\text{g kg}_{\text{DW}}^{-1}$)								
BioSS	87	7.8	44.5	21.0 ± 0.3	5.1 ± 1.1	2.9 ± 0.1	4.3 ± 0.1	9.1 ± 0.2	0.16	0.33	0.14	0.26
Bio400	–	7.6	48.0	54.5 ± 0.4	11.6 ± 0.4	8.0 ± 0.2	10.9 ± 0.1	23.8 ± 0.3	0.17	0.34	0.12	0.26
Bio600	–	6.4	43.8	67.5 ± 1.6	19.1 ± 3.5	10.7 ± 0.6	13.6 ± 0.3	29.7 ± 0.7	0.18	0.34	0.16	0.26
FeSS	77	4.1	32.4	22.3 ± 0.6	29.1 ± 1.4	8.4 ± 0.1	4.6 ± 0.1	49.1 ± 0.6	0.43	1.70	0.72	0.26
Fe400	–	3.4	29.0	43.3 ± 1.0	67.0 ± 0.8	15.1 ± 0.2	7.1 ± 0.2	77.3 ± 1.6	0.40	1.38	0.86	0.21
Fe600	–	2.5	23.6	51.6 ± 1.6	79.7 ± 0.8	23.8 ± 7.4	8.4 ± 0.3	92.4 ± 2.6	0.53	1.38	0.86	0.21

mineral associated with them. Table 2 shows that the Al:P, Ca:P and Fe:P molar ratios for the FeSS and its derived biochars were approximately two, four and five times higher, respectively, than for the BioSS and its biochars.

3.2. XRD and SEM-EDS

No crystalline phosphate minerals were detected by PXRD for biomaterials (Figs. S2 and S3). Reflections from silica (quartz), which became more pronounced with temperature treatments, were observed for all samples. For FeSS, reflections from crystalline CaCO_3 were observed in accordance with the high calcium concentration based on ICP-OES measurements (Table 2). Higher Ca:P and Fe:P molar ratios in FeSS, Fe400, and Fe600 (Table 2) than BioSS, Bio400 and Bio600 led to the observed co-localization of Ca and Fe with P by SEM-EDS (Table S2). Meanwhile, Ca-P colocalization was observed in BioSS and its biochars while Fe-P colocalization was not observed.

3.3. P XANES

The best fits of the P K-edge LCFs for the different sludges and biochar are shown in Table 3. The results of the LCF should be interpreted with caution, considering the uncertainties associated with this analysis. LCF is a mathematical method that itself already has uncertainties of approximately 10% for much less complex mixtures of compounds (Werner and Priezel, 2015). Difficulties using XANES LCF for biochars may arise from (1) their heterogeneity, (2) an initial set of incomplete standards for complex samples containing a large range of P compounds and (3) the difficulty of distinguishing very similar P species using bulk XANES (Huang and Tang, 2016). Nonetheless, LCF provides valuable insight into the most likely associations of P with Fe, Al, and Ca, as well as its polymeric forms such as pyrophosphate, and potentially organic forms of P, thereby allowing for the identification of binding configurations without changing the chemical forms during analysis, such as by chemical extraction.

As indicated by the LCF, the original sludges (BioSS and FeSS) shared features with phytate, Ca-bound phosphate, and vivianite. Phytate was the standard used in this linear combination fitting, but represents all organic phosphate compounds and other featureless phosphates like phosphate adsorbed to organic compounds. It has been speculated that, carbon condensation occurring during pyrolysis may lead to some adsorption or occlusion of phosphate within the carbon matrix (Huang and Tang, 2015; Müller-Stöver et al., 2021; Rathnayake et al., 2023). This may be in line with Barrow's (2021) description of phosphate dynamics in soil following the adsorption-penetration theory, in which solid state diffusion of phosphate occurs, a process which may be enhanced if temperatures are increased (like in pyrolysis) and the activation energy is overcome.

In a similar way, the inclusion of amorphous calcium phosphate, $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, and hydroxyapatite in the LCF does not necessarily indicate that these compounds are present but rather that there is some association between Ca and P (Figs. S4 and S5, with annotated examples of

Table 3

Linear combination fitting of X-ray Absorption Near Edge Spectroscopy (XANES) spectra obtained by analysis of the P K-edge of biomaterials. HAP stands for hydroxyapatite and ‘-’ indicates the standard was not included in the LCF. Values for the different components are given as percentages (based on phosphorus content). Values after \pm indicate standard error.

P speciation	Calcium phosphates			Iron phosphates	Organic phosphate	Phosphoanhydride bond	NH ₄ /Mg associated phosphate		Sum	R-Factor
	Standard	HAP	Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Ca ₂ O ₇ P ₂ xH ₂ O	Vivianite	Phytate	Na-pyrophosphate	Struvite		
BioSS	0 ± 4	-	28 ± 4	6 ± 7	66 ± 4	0 ± 3	-	-	100	0.0023
Bio400	5 ± 2	-	39 ± 4	13 ± 1	0 ± 3	43 ± 2	-	-	100	0.0014
Bio600	22 ± 3	-	20 ± 6	12 ± 1	0 ± 4	46 ± 3	-	-	100	0.0026
FeSS	-	7 ± 3	-	18 ± 2	73 ± 3	-	-	7 ± 5	105	0.0055
Fe400	-	33 ± 3	-	20 ± 2	51 ± 3	-	-	0 ± 5	104	0.0068
Fe600	-	47 ± 3	-	12 ± 2	44 ± 3	-	-	0 ± 5	103	0.0069

spectral features in Fig. S5 sample Fe400), as we observed a slight post K-edge feature around 2164 eV. These features were also present in the derived sewage sludge biochars. The detection of vivianite indicates an association between iron and phosphate. On examination of the spectra, a pre-edge feature around 2150 eV, indicative of Fe-P minerals, was observed for the FeSS and only slightly for FeSS derived biochars (Fig. S5). These also had slightly higher fractions of iron associated P (12–20%) than BioSS and its biochars (6–13%) as indicated by the vivianite present in the LCFs.

Additionally, upon inspection of the Fe K-edge LCF results (Table S3), we observe that the Fe in the FeSS was more likely to be associated with phosphate (58% Fe associated with P) than the Fe in the BioSS (21% Fe associated with P). After thermal treatment, the Bio400 and Bio600 had slightly higher proportions of Fe associated with phosphate (45% and 53% Fe associated with P respectively), while Fe400 and Fe600 had similar amounts of Fe associated with P compared to the original sludge (50% and 46% of the total Fe intensity, respectively).

The FeSS also showed a minor struvite fraction (7%) in the P K edge LCF, indicating associations of phosphate with magnesium and nitrogen, which are not evident in the biochars. The FeSS-derived biochars contained predominantly phytate-like fractions of phosphorus, again indicating organic or phosphate adsorbed to organics, while the BioSS-derived biochars showed a significant fraction of pyrophosphates (about 45% each). While each of the spectra was fitted to standards to the best of our ability, Figs. S4 and S5 show incomplete fittings, which indicate that we cannot exclude the possibility of unknown, other P species present in the samples. Thus, the shortcomings in the mathematical fitting of the spectra, the difficulties in distinguishing features in bulk XANES analysis, and some self-absorption during analysis due to high P concentrations emphasize the need to verify speciation determined using XANES with other methods.

3.4. Liquid state ³¹P NMR spectroscopy

The NMR spectra (Table 4, Figs. S6 and S7) show that the FeSS contained mainly inorganic ortho-P (86% of P according to the total integrated intensity) after dewatering at the wastewater treatment

Table 4

Characterization of P compounds by ³¹P NMR reported as relative abundance (% based on the integrated spectral intensity) in concentrated NaOH extracts. ND denotes not detected, indicating concentrations below 3–5%.

Sample	Inorg orthoP	Monoesters	Diesters	Poly-P (end)	Pyro-P	Poly-P (middle)
δ (ppm)	5.8	4.5	4.3	-4.2	-4.6	-18.5
BioSS	76	11	12	ND	0.5	ND
Bio400	14	ND	ND	22	51	12
Bio600	18	ND	ND	6	66	10
FeSS	85.9	7.0	5.5	ND	1.6	ND
Fe400	95.5	ND	ND	ND	4.5	ND
Fe600	100	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND

plant, as well as small amounts of organic species (7% monoesters and 6% diesters) and pyro-P (2%). After pyrolysis, even at only 400 °C, no organic species were detected in the NaOH extracts. Pyrophosphates were detected after pyrolysis at 400 °C for the FeSS (5%), but not at 600 °C. Comparatively, the relative abundance of the organic species was higher in the BioSS than in the FeSS, probably due to the EBPR treatment of the BioSS. However, pyrolysis increased the pyro-P content in the extract (51% for Bio400 and 66% for Bio600), and to a lesser extent poly-P (34% for Bio400 and 16% for Bio600).

3.5. Sequential extraction

The proportion of phosphate in each fraction is shown in Fig. 1. This

Fig. 1. The relative concentration (percentage) of total P extracted for each of the fractions in the sequential extraction protocol (water, NaHCO₃, NaOH, and HCl). Theoretical P of solids remaining following extraction are part of the unaccounted P fraction (measurement uncertainty may therefore lead to negative values like FeSS). Error bars represent standard errors.

clearly shows that a significantly higher percentage (53% inorganic P and 3% organic P) of the total phosphorus was water-extractable for the BioSS. Combined with a relatively high bicarbonate extractable fraction (14% inorganic P and 1% organic P), this suggests that the biologically treated sludge had a much higher labile phosphorus pool than the iron precipitated FeSS (1% water extractable inorganic P, 10% bicarbonate extractable inorganic P and 1% bicarbonate extractable organic P) or

any of the biochar counterparts. Consequently, the extractable ortho-P in the NaOH fraction (42% inorganic P and 3% organic P for FeSS and 9% inorganic P and 3% organic P for BioSS) and the HCl fraction (54% inorganic P for FeSS and 6% inorganic P and 2% organic P for BioSS) was greater for the FeSS than for the BioSS. For all biochars, the water and bicarbonate extractable fractions decreased as compared to the original sludges. There was about a 25-fold and 5-fold decrease in WEP and

Fig. 2. Water-extractable phosphorus measurements (mg P per gram soil) at different distances from the biomaterial and respective soil interface at two weeks, four weeks, and 14 weeks incubation as a layer in the loamy and sandy soils.

bicarbonate extractable P, respectively, for the BioSS biochars compared to BioSS, and a 2-fold decrease in bicarbonate extractable P for the FeSS biochars compared to FeSS. Biochars of the same origin but pyrolyzed at different temperatures were generally similar in the amounts of P extracted by each of the different extractants.

3.6. Mobility of P upon incubation of biomaterials in two different soils

In all setups, water extractable phosphorus (WEP) was significantly higher than the control (soil background WEP) within the biomaterial layer and decreased to control level at different distances (Fig. 2). Only for the BioSS did WEP levels remain significantly above the control soil level up to 3 mm from the biomaterial layer in all soils and for all

Fig. 3. Difference in pH from negative control (no biomaterials added) at different distances from the biomaterial:soil interface after incubating biomaterials for two weeks, four weeks, and 14 weeks as a layer in the loamy and sandy soils.

incubation times (Table S4, p-adjusted values ranged from 0.04 to 0.008). The WEP at the biomaterial layer was also about 3 times higher for the BioSS than for the FeSS and 6 times higher than for most biochars at 2- and 4-weeks incubation. For the FeSS and all biochars, there was also a much steeper decrease to the control WEP than for the BioSS with each successive distance from the biomaterial layer (Fig. 2), indicating less diffusion of bioavailable P out of these biomaterials.

The WEP decreased (or remained at a very similar level) with a longer incubation time of 14 weeks for all materials in the biomaterial layer. For example, when BioSS was applied to the sandy soil, 13.2% of the total applied P was water extractable at the biomaterial layer after two weeks of incubation, while this decreased to 5.1% after 14 weeks of incubation. For the loamy soil this decrease was from 17.0% P to 6.0% P in the biomaterial layer. The decrease in WEP in soil layers further away from the biomaterial layer was dependent on the initial propensity of the biomaterial to release labile WEP.

The effect of BioSS on pH was also more pronounced at greater distances from the biomaterial layer than that of FeSS and all biochars (Fig. 3). While FeSS addition to the soils led to a higher pH at the biomaterial layer (7.1, 6.7 and 6.6 at two, four, and 14 weeks respectively), it decreased to the control level for both the sandy (5.6) and loamy (6.5) soils within 1 or 2 mm. However, the application of BioSS resulted in an increase in the pH of the biomaterial layer two weeks after incubation, with effects extending to all distances. In the loamy soil, there was an increase in pH (from 6.5 at control level) after two weeks of incubation with pH measurements ranging from 7.6 to 8.2 in the first three mm and a range of 7.1–8.0 at further distances. After four weeks of incubation, a tapering to below the control pH was observed (range of 5.5–6.4 at distances greater than 2 mm) and after 14 weeks, a drop in pH to values between 5 and 6 could be seen at all sampling distances. A similar trend was observed for the sandy soil, with pH values dropping below control levels already after two weeks of incubation (range 5.3–4.8 at 5–11 mm distances) and even more after four and 14 weeks of incubation (5.1–4.7 at distances greater than 1 mm after four weeks and 4.7–4.6 at all distances after 14 weeks).

4. Discussion

4.1. Material characterization and P speciation

Table 2 shows that the Ca:P and Fe:P ratios for FeSS and derived biochars are both about 5 times higher than for BioSS and derived biochars. This suggests that associations (sorbed or precipitated) between P and Fe, as well as P and Ca, are higher for FeSS and derived biochars. We also observed more colocalization of P and Fe, as well as P and Ca, in the SEM-EDS elemental maps of FeSS, Fe400 and Fe600 than in the other biomaterials, again suggesting stronger associations (Table S2). The XRD diffractograms suggest that the unmodified sludge materials contained predominantly X-ray amorphous P phases, i.e. amorphous or nanocrystalline materials (e.g. $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$), as has been reported previously (Buss et al., 2020; Shober et al., 2006, Qian and Jiang, 2014; Wang et al., 2012).

Further insight into the P speciation in biomaterials was provided by XANES. The LCF showed that the original sludges had both associations of P with Fe (vivianite) and Ca (HAP, amorphous calcium phosphate and $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$) and contained organic and/or organically adsorbed phosphate (phytate). This is in line with other studies that have shown that the major P species present in sludges are Al/Fe adsorbed phosphate, calcium phosphate and components with a spectrum similar to phytic acid (Huang and Tang, 2016; Shober et al., 2006). The ratio of phytate in the sludges decreased after pyrolysis, while the ratios of Fe- and Ca-associated phosphate increased. This trend is consistent with the enrichment of Fe, Ca, and P in biochars (Table 2) and the decrease in organic P (Table 4).

The formation of pyrophosphate in Bio400 and Bio600 with temperature treatment was found using both XANES and ^{31}P NMR. Other

studies have also found this increase in pyrophosphates and short-chain polyphosphates with pyrolysis of EBPR sludges (Huang and Tang, 2015; Qian et al., 2019). This may be due to the breakdown of previously present polyphosphates (Robinson et al., 2018). Alternatively, in lower-temperature biochars (<600 °C), ortho-P may undergo dehydration reactions to become pyro-P, or organic P in the sludges may be converted to pyro-P (Qian and Jiang, 2014). The organic carbon in these lower-temperature biochars may stabilize pyrophosphate by allowing for complexation (with or without a bridging metal) (Uchimiya et al., 2015). This is likely to be enhanced by carboxyl and hydroxyl groups in the organic matter binding to cations such as Ca(II) and Mg(II), which then reduces the ability of P to bind to these elements and thereby the ability to form recalcitrant P minerals (Lu et al., 2013). An increased proportion of poly- or pyrophosphates has previously been associated with increased P plant availability (Torres-Dorante et al., 2006). For this reason, Qian et al. (2020) have suggested that EBPR sludge biochars may be promising as fertilizers.

Additionally, Li et al. (2018b) showed that in sludges with fewer organic components, only orthophosphate peaks are observed in ^{31}P NMR spectra, which was corroborated by our study of the FeSS using both liquid state NMR and XANES. Qian and Jiang (2014) showed a similar speciation sequence from sludges to biochars as for the FeSS, with ortho-P and organic fractions as well as pyro-P initially present, followed by removal of organic fractions and degradation of pyro-P after pyrolysis.

After pyrolysis treatment, XANES LCF detected a 20–27% increase in the amount of P associated with Ca or Fe minerals compared to the original sludges. This increase was largely attributed to an increase in Ca-associated minerals, with a 16% increase in Ca-associated minerals for Bio400/600 and 26% and 40% increases for Fe400 and Fe600 respectively. This is consistent with the expectation that pyrolysis increases mineral and inorganic associations as organic matter degrades (Figueiredo et al., 2021; Jin et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2013). This trend is not as clear for the Fe-associated fractions, but from the Fe K-edge results, the association of Fe with P appeared to be higher in FeSS and its resulting biochars compared to the BioSS (particularly low associations with P), most likely due to FeClSO_4 precipitation during wastewater treatment, which increased Fe content in the biomaterials (Table 2).

For all characterization methods used, there is a large effect of pyrolysis on speciation generally, but only subtle difference between those created at 400 °C and 600 °C. This raises the question of the extent to which increases in pyrolysis temperature (e.g. by 200 °C) affect biochar P mobility in soils, as well as P bioavailability, despite only observing minor differences in P speciation (Laan et al., 2023; Li et al., 2018a). The relationship between P speciation derived from these characterization methods and P lability and mobility in soils is not clear (Rose et al., 2019; van der Bom et al., 2022), and needs to be explored in combination with other methods, such as sequential extraction (for P lability) or one-dimensional soil incubations (for mobility).

4.2. Insight into lability of different P pools through sequential extraction

Extractants are operationally defined, with extractants increasing in strength successively extracting less labile P fractions. While many have tried to provide more concrete evidence of chemicals extracting specific P phases (NaHCO_3 -P extracts Al and Fe sorbed inorganic P and easily mineralized organic P, NaOH extracts amorphous Al and Fe P phases and more stable organic P, and HCl extracts Ca bound P), this has also been fundamentally questioned (Barrow et al., 2021; Toor et al., 2006). Throughout our experiments, the sequential extraction was used to gain insight into P fractions of different lability, with the water and bicarbonate extractable fractions representing a fraction that is most likely to be plant available.

The BioSS had the highest labile P fraction (56% water and 15% bicarbonate extractable) of all the biomaterials. In comparison, the FeSS had 1% water and 11% bicarbonate extractable P. A labile P fraction as

high as the BioSS is unusual, even for EBPR sludges, which may contain less metal-bound P. In the literature, WEP values are typically less than 3% for dewatered EBPR sludges (Petriglieri et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022). Nonetheless, higher values have been measured, for e.g. 20.7% by Qian and Jiang (2014) and 16.8% by Ylivainio et al. (2021). The BioSS high lability compared to other sludges is likely due to very low amount of metal-bound P, as discussed in section 4.1, as well as a large fraction of the sewage sludge originating from bread and dairy waste streams (H. Hansen, personal communication, October 19, 2023).

Greater NaOH (5 times) and HCl (10 times) extractable P was found for the FeSS than the BioSS, likely due to greater association with Fe and Al (increasing NaOH extractable P) and Ca (increasing HCl extractable P), as has been indicated by ICP-OES, XANES and SEM-EDS. A large NaOH pool for iron-treated sludges (50% or more of the total P) has been shown in the literature (Alvarenga et al., 2017; Falk Øgaard and Brod, 2016; Ylivainio et al., 2021). In fact, this pool often contains the largest extractable P fraction, whereas for the FeSS, the HCl fraction was larger than the NaOH fraction, which was also the case for FeSS derived biochars. A larger HCl than NaOH fraction in the FeSS and its biochars may be due to a high calcium content in some Danish sewage sludges from wastewater treatment plants on Zealand (due to a high CaCO₃ content in the water), which leads to more P-Ca bonds that are more easily solubilized by HCl. This was also suggested by Lemming et al. (2020) and Sica et al. (2023). This was not shown for the BioSS materials, which originate from a municipality in Jutland that according to measurements in 2010 has 'medium hard' water (8–12 °dH), whereas the FeSS wastewater treatment plant is in an area where the water hardness ranges from 'fairly hard' (12–18 °dH) to 'hard' (18–30 °dH) (Hardness of Danish drinking water, 2010).

Generally, biochars had a much lower labile (water and NaHCO₃) fraction than the original sludges due to conversion to less labile P minerals during pyrolysis (Bridle and Pritchard, 2004; Qian and Jiang, 2014). However, we did not see clear differences between the different pools for biochars produced at 400 °C and 600 °C, which indicates similar P lability for these biochars (Tiessen and Moir, 2007). While different pyrolysis temperatures often give rise to differences in extractability (Figueiredo et al., 2021; Uchimiya and Hiradate, 2014), this is not always the case (Xu et al., 2016).

In literature, a general shift from labile fractions in the sewage sludges to the NaOH fractions is observed, particularly for low temperature biochars, and a shift to HCl fractions with higher temperature treatments (Li et al., 2018b; Qian and Jiang, 2014). The Bio600 and Bio400 had a much lower NaOH extractable P fraction than the Fe600 and Fe400. A smaller NaOH pool may also have implications for their ability to serve as a 'slow release' fertilizer, as some researchers have linked this intermediately available P pool to the ability to supply the P slowly, yet with some consistency, over a longer time (Schneider and Haderlein, 2016). This relationship, however, is still not very clear.

The larger NaOH pool for Fe400 and Fe600 may again be related to the higher amounts of Fe in the FeSS and its subsequent biochars. The HCl extractable fraction was of similar magnitude for the BioSS-derived biochars and the FeSS-derived biochars. However, it was observed that a much larger proportion of the P in the HCl fraction was found in the organic fraction. It should be noted that the original extraction protocol was developed for soil, and subsequently adopted (with varying solid: liquid ratios) for sludge and biochars (Li et al., 2018a; Qian and Jiang, 2014). Pyrolysis significantly affects P speciation dynamics and increases polymeric phosphate species, as discussed previously, which is likely to affect the species that are extracted in each step of the sequential extraction. Therefore, the organic P found in the HCl fraction are unlikely to be true organic species as they are not often extracted by 1 mol L⁻¹ HCl (Tiessen and Moir, 2007). It may be pyrophosphate species present in the extract that were only measurable after full digestion, especially considering that NMR analysis of BioSS biochars showed an increased proportion of pyrophosphates (Condron and Newman, 2011).

While we gain insight into P solubility within materials, sequential extractions do not consider many biotic (e.g. microorganisms) and abiotic (e.g. texture) soil factors. The batch experimental nature of the extractions may also simulate larger mass transfer to liquids than is realistic for soil pore waters, and often does not allow for accurate simulation of reabsorption to soil phases. We therefore used the 1D incubation setups to gain a greater understanding of P at the soil-biomaterial interface.

4.3. Mobility of plant-available P within biomaterials in two soils after two, four and fourteen weeks of incubation

Close to a fertilizer band, the high P concentration would ensure that precipitation reactions dominate (Lombi et al., 2005), while at greater distances, adsorption to soil components dominates (McLaughlin et al., 2011). However, Meyer et al. (2023) found that P availability was regulated by precipitation reactions up to 25 mm from the band. As these precipitation reactions are determined by which elements have higher concentrations than the solubility products of their P compounds, the elemental concentrations within the fertilizer band (Fe, Al, Ca, etc.), as well as the P speciation already present, become relevant. The dynamics of solubility and precipitation are strongly affected by soil pH.

The higher WEP in the biomaterial layer and adjacent layers for the sludges than the biochar counterparts suggested more mobile/bioavailable P for these materials (Lemming et al., 2017), particularly for the BioSS (Fig. 2). This is consistent with the high proportion of labile P within the BioSS as demonstrated by sequential extraction. The high WEP concentration in BioSS is especially noteworthy, as only 25 mg P was added per incubation setup in this treatment, compared to 40 mg P for all other biomaterials. In this sense, the P speciation (lower association of P in BioSS with Ca or Fe compared to the FeSS) had clear consequences for P lability.

The effect of BioSS on pH at greater distances from the biomaterial layer was also more pronounced than that of FeSS (Fig. 3). The decrease in pH at longer incubation periods for the BioSS could be due to the higher N content of the sludge (7.8% for BioSS and 4.1% for FeSS), which provides NH₄⁺ for nitrification (Msimbira and Smith, 2020). Additionally, the decomposition of organic matter can lead to CO₂ being released, which, when dissolved in soil pore water, may become H₂CO₃, leading to a decrease in pH (Bolan et al., 1991). The fact that this acidification was only observed at greater distances from the biomaterial with shorter incubation periods may be due to the more alkaline biomaterial buffering the pH at distances close to it, while soluble organic matter may already have diffused to greater distances. Additionally, with increased microbial activity due to sludge addition, it may be that microbial transport plays a role in displacement of C and N sources.

Although this acidification could lead to more calcium-associated phosphate becoming available from soils through mineral dissolution, this effect was not clearly demonstrated. In fact, with longer incubation periods, we saw less WEP in most biomaterials and adjacent soil layers. Meyer et al., 2021, 2023) showed that in fertilizer hotspots, even at pH ranges between 3.5 and 7.5, aluminum was the dominant phase determining P availability, whereas sorption reactions with Fe and Ca were less important. It may therefore be that as pH decreases, more of the P is fixed by precipitation of Al-P compounds (Lindsay, 1979). We have no indication of the extent of Al-P precipitation in this experiment, but we measured higher Al_{ox} phases in the sandy soil (32 and 109 mmol kg⁻¹ for the loamy and sandy soils respectively), which may explain some of the decrease in WEP in the BioSS with longer incubation in this soil, as well as a slightly lower WEP at two weeks incubation. Nevertheless, increased P sorption or precipitation also occurred in the loamy soil with longer incubation time.

It may also be that microbial immobilization played a role in reducing phosphorus availability with increasing incubation time. Hotspots of biomaterials, such as sewage sludge, may lead to an increase

in microbial activity in the adjacent soil, leading to some immobilization of the P from these materials (Richardson and Simpson, 2011; Spohn and Kuzuyakov, 2013). With longer incubation periods, more of this microbial growth may occur and increased incorporation into biological structures may take place.

Very little decrease in WEP was observed for the FeSS with longer incubation and no real decrease was observed for the biochars, likely due to low initial WEP values at two weeks incubation. For the biochars, it was observed that at 1 and 2 mm, Bio400 and Bio600 had a tendency towards higher WEP values than the control across the different soils and incubation periods than the Fe400 and Fe600 (Fig. S2, Table S4). However, the trends are too unclear to draw definitive links between P speciation within the biochars, P lability in the materials and eventual soil mobility. Differences between P mobility of different biochars may have been magnified if a pure biochar biomaterial layer were used instead of a sand/biochar mixture, as the contact between biochar and soil would have been more direct, thus allowing for better P diffusion. However, P application rates would have had to be far higher for the biochars, therefore making it difficult to compare these treatments with their original sludges. We can however conclude a large decrease in P lability and mobility upon pyrolysis of the sewage sludges, which indicates a low propensity for P leaching but may indicate difficulties for use as a P fertilizer. For the BioSS on the other hand, the risk to P leaching is greater, but the potential for use as P fertilizer is also greater. Further testing, both in pots and long-term field trials, is required to determine the performance of the materials as P fertilizers and their potential for P leaching.

(Sun et al., 2022b) demonstrated some transformation of Ca-P in sewage sludge biochars to soluble plant-available P over a three-month period. Such potential for transformation and 'slow release' P fertilization was not demonstrated here, most likely due to the absence of a plant sink. It should also be noted that water extractable P was used to reflect plant availability in this study, which prevents conclusions about how much total phosphorus diffuses out of the biomaterial layer and could subsequently change in availability over time due to changing abiotic and biotic factors (Sica et al., 2023). As the total P concentration diffuses out of the biomaterial and reaches the soil layers, soil properties become important in determining P availability. Contrary to our expectations, we did not find large differences in water extractable P between the different soils, although this may be largely due to the general immobility of the P within the biochars. However, also for the BioSS, which contained the highest labile and mobile P fraction, we did not see differences between the WEP in the two soils beyond the biomaterial layer. Effects of the different soils may become more evident with longer incubation periods or when the biomaterials are applied to soils in the presence of a plant sink.

5. Conclusions

The speciation of P in sludges and derived biochars was clearly dependent on whether biological P removal or iron addition was used for P removal at the wastewater treatment plant. This led to more Ca and Fe mineral associations for the FeSS and its biochars than the BioSS and its biochars. Additionally, more than 40% more pyro- and polyphosphates were detected in the EBPR-treated Bio400 and Bio600 than in the Fe400 and Fe600. Differences in P speciation between the different biochars were, however, not reflected in the incubation experiment, as all biochars remained relatively immobile, regardless of the original feedstock or maximum pyrolysis temperature. This immobility observed in soil is strongly related to a lack of labile (water and bicarbonate extractable) P, as observed in sequential chemical extraction.

The BioSS, on the other hand, contained a lot of labile P and, when incubated in the two soils, was also the only material for which water-extractable P remained significantly above the control soil level up to 3 mm from the biomaterial layer. This was a clear consequence of P

speciation, as the material contains very few metal phases (Fe, Al, and Ca) that may immobilize phosphate. This wider diffusion of potentially plant available P may have positive implications for the biomaterial as a phosphorus fertilizer but may also pose a risk of facilitated leaching of phosphorus into the environment if plants do not take up most of this applied phosphorus. However, we have shown that some of the available P in the sewage sludges decreased in the soil over the course of a three-month incubation period, indicating that some of this available P is sorbed or otherwise immobilized to soil phases.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Josephine Kooij: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Puu-Tai Yang:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Formal analysis. **Sander Bruun:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Jakob Magid:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Ulla Gro Nielsen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Luise Theil Kuhn:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Dorette Müller-Stöver:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

I have shared my data at <https://doi.org/10.17894/ucph.7bb23919-340c-42a0-94c4-11f87e707148>

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions RecaP Project [grant number 956454].

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.122565>.

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